

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**MISCONCEPTION REGARDING GENERIC AND BRAND
DRUGS**

Aamir Z. Khan *, **Omkar B. Khalkar**, **Shubham J. Khairnar***, **Anil G. Jadhav**
Sandip Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Mahiravani, Nashik Pin.422213.

Abstract:

The main focus of our article is that generic drug is same that of branded drugs in active ingredients, mode of administration, safety and dosage. Government of India has given permission to generic drug in prescription. FDA (Food and Drugs Administration) also conveyed that generic drugs are safe as the branded drugs. Use of generic drug instead of branded drug saves lots of money; branded drugs are costlier and lead to higher expenditure.

The present article tells us the similarities between branded and generic drug. Only due to some myths and lack of knowledge people avoid generic drug but it will clear now with this article.

Corresponding author:

Mr. Aamir Z. Khan,
Sandip Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences,
Mahiravani, Nashik Pin.422213.
Contact no. 7741899120,7020387926
Email Address: sunnykhairnar62@gmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Aamir Z. Khan et al, *Misconception Regarding Generic And Brand Drugs*,
Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(08).

INTRODUCTION:

We all are familiar to generic and branded drug but only in the aspect that generic drug is less costly than branded drug, also branded drug provide quick relief. But actually, the generic and branded drugs are same in active ingredient, route of admin, dosage, mode of action and safety. Branded drugs are developed by big companies they have patent of that particular drug, branded drugs are named such that they can be easily spelled and remembered. The companies invest a lot in research, safety test, FDA trials hence they sell the drug at higher prices.

The characteristics of branded drugs are:

- High cost
- High quality
- High margin for retailer
- High investment

While generic drugs are the same copy of branded drugs means which brand name drugs patent expires it open for all as a result the generic companies now use that formulation and sell it as generic drug with generic name.

Eg. : Crocin is a brand name while Paracetamol is a generic drug.

Earlier generic drugs were not used as much now a day. Today around 80-85 % of brand name drugs are available in generic form. Generic drugs are cost saver, every year billions of rupees are saved due to generic drugs.

Government of India is also helping and creating awareness about generic drugs. Hence, it is important that we use generic drugs instead of brand name drugs because it will prove to less expenditure in Pharmaceuticals.

Lack of knowledge and awareness is responsible for not using generic drugs[1].

The difference and similarities between generic and branded drugs:

The main and major difference in generic and branded drugs is its name. Eg. Paracetamol is a generic drug Crocin is a branded drug or brand name of Paracetamol. For ads easy spell different companies giving particular name to the drug. It may also differ in color, flavour, shape and packing. And if we talk about similarities then all the ingredients, size, dosage form, effectiveness, mode of action everything is similar [2].

Sr.no.	Branded Drugs	Generic Drugs
1.	The “look” of branded drugs are Familiar to consumers.	The “look” of generic drugs may be Slightly differ from branded drugs.
2.	The trade name of branded drugs are unique than others.	The generic drugs have no trade names.
3.	Branded drugs are protected by patents of a single company.	These are low cost version of branded drugs.
4.	Drug prices are decided by pharmaceutical companies are Regulated by Federal Patents.	Drug prices are decided and regulated by particular Manufacturing company.
5.	Market by single company.	Produced by generic companies once the patent on branded drug expires.

Myths and misconceptions about Generic drugs and Branded drugs:

As generic drugs are cheaper and less expensive than branded drugs there are many misbeliefs about it.

- People think that they have to compromise with the quality of drug, safety and is less effective than branded drugs. But we all have to understand that all drugs are manufactured by FDA (Foods and Drug Administration) standards and safety.
- Another myth is generic drug take longer time to show its effects, i.e. they are not quick in action.
- Generic drugs have side effects due to low quality.

The thing which we have to understand is that almost 60% of the brand name drug companies manufacture generic drug. Only lack of knowledge and awareness are responsible for these myths and misconceptions.

Why generic medicines are not so popular?

The main reason is advertisements, branded drugs and companies spends a lot for advertisements on all the platforms as a result people get aware of them and their names are fixed in people mind, while on the other hand generic drugs are not shown in ads and people are not aware of its names. Also lack of knowledge is also the one reason.

Also due to the misbeliefs the generic drugs are not popular. Government is trying to implement the use of generic medicine in treatment.

Why branded drugs are costlier and doctors mainly prescribes Branded drugs?

The branded drugs are manufactured by big companies they have patent, lots of investment is required for the research of a drug, marketing, advertisement which results in higher prices of branded drugs.

Also doctor's prescription includes branded drugs because they are majorly aware of branded drugs. Different drug companies give the list of branded drug to the doctors which are released newly and the easy spell of branded drug. Its availability in the market also forces them to prescribe branded drugs.

How the generic drugs do receive FDA approval?

- ✓ The main aspect of receiving FDA approval is that the generic drug should meet some standards.
- ✓ Firstly, the drug companies need to submit a ANDA (Abbreviated New Drug Application)

which is required for approval of generic drug for their selling in a market.

The ANDA should show that the generic drug is equivalent to branded drug in some ways.

1. Same active ingredient as that of branded drug.
2. The route of administration should be same.
3. The drug should be manufactured under strict standards in the way which branded drugs are manufactured.
4. Label and container should be appropriate.
5. The shelf life of medicine should be same as that of branded drug.

Drawbacks of Branded drugs over Generic drug:

According to FDA (food & drug administration) the generic and branded contains same active ingredient (API), the price of branded drugs are more costly than generic drugs. This is major drawback of branded drugs. This factor matters lots in case of financially backward people, which cannot afford the branded medications. Sometimes the brands tries to make the maximum profit by advertising marketing, which makes confusion among common people to make a wise decision between generic and branded drugs.

The branded company have their medical representative (MR) creates lot of misconception between branded and generic drug. The MR always makes their efforts to promote their brand medicine.

There is marketing problem with branded drugs, sometimes the patient of pharmacist refuse to buy the particular brand drug.

Should we shift our preference towards generic drug?

In above discussion we are cleared with myths and misconceptions between both. In India the demand for the generic drugs is increasing day-by-day. By considering this fact we can now shift or preference towards the generic drugs, the basic reason is their availability and cost effectiveness. Previously the availability of generic drugs are not so available in normal medical store. Recently due to increasing in demand the pharmacist started to dispense the generic drugs in market [3].

CONCLUSION:

The overall study of Generic and Branded drugs teaches us that there is almost no difference between generic and Branded. The misbeliefs, ads, lack of awareness about generic drug are responsible for higher sale of Branded drugs.

But price difference should be considered along with the same product. Nearly more than 80% of Branded drugs are available in generic drug forms.

Also use of generic drugs will save billions of rupees.

REFERENCES:

1. Patil S; Short Communication on- Generic versus branded drugs; Pharma tutor; 2019; 16-17; <http://dx.doi.org/10.29161/PT.v7.i2.2019.16>
2. Davit(2009); comparing generic and innovator drugs; A 12 years of bioequivalence data from the united states Food and Drug Administrator; Ann Pharmacother; 43(10);1583-1597
3. Gaither C.A., kirking D.M., Ascione F. And Welage L.S.(2001);consumers views on generic medication; J. of the American Pharma. Asso; 41(5)729-736